

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand formation curves.

of ionic character may be suggested to the metal-ligand bonding, the plots, however, do not exhibit any complete linear relationship. Such a difference in the trend of stability constant is not uncommon in the case of lanthanide complexes¹¹⁻¹³ and this may be due to varying degree of stabilization arising out of interaction of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field¹⁴.

The absence of 1:2 chelates in the present case may be due to steric hindrance produced by the attached ligand in the 1:1 chelate to the approach of the second one.

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Potentiometric Studies of Metal Chelates of Tiron with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III)

B. C. BHUYAN and S. N. DUBEY*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

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ALTHOUGH chelating properties of tiron have been reported with a number of metals¹⁻³, no attempt appears to have been made to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of its chelates with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III). In the present communication, the proton-ligand stability constants of tiron, the thermodynamic stability constants of its chelates with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III) and thermodynamic changes (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) accompanying complex formation have been reported.

Experimental

The solution of beryllium sulphate (Russian), copper sulphate (BDH, AR) and aluminium nitrate (E. Merck) were prepared in double distilled water and standardised by standard analytical methods. The solutions of tiron (Hopkins and Williams, England) and sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were also prepared in double distilled water. The pH-titrations were carried out at varying ionic strengths (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3M) and temperatures (30° and 40°) with a Phillips precision pH meter (PR 9405M) using standard glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

The Calvin Bjerrum titration technique^{4,5} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ has been used to

* To whom correspondence should be made,

TABLE 1—THE FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF TIRON COMPLEXES WITH Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III)

Metal ion	30°, $\mu=0.1 M$			30°, $\mu=0.2 M$			30°, $\mu=0.3 M$			40°, $\mu=0.1 M$		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
H ⁺	11.05	7.75	—	10.85	7.63	—	10.67	7.56	—	10.67	7.60	—
Be ²⁺	12.51	10.66	—	12.18	10.17	—	11.04	9.17	—	11.18	8.23	—
Cu ²⁺	15.08	13.69	—	14.80	13.34	—	14.14	12.76	—	13.70	12.30	—
Al ³⁺	15.48	14.61	12.72	14.78	13.92	12.43	14.39	13.48	12.15	15.33	14.36	12.45

	ΔG (k. cal./mole)		ΔH (k. cal./mole)	ΔS (e. u.)
	30°C	40°C	30°C	35°C
Be ²⁺	-32.67	-27.37	-163.34	-424.04
Cu ²⁺	-40.57	-36.66	-120.33	-258.86
Al ³⁺	-60.37	-59.42	-29.22	98.36

The thermodynamic formation constants $\log K^{\mu=0}$ for Be (II), Cu(II) and Al (III)-tiron complexes were found to be 13.24, 11.50, 15.63, 14.04, 16.00, 15.18 and 13.00 respectively.

determine the formation constants of tiron and the formation constants of its complexes with Be(II), Cu(II) and Al(III). The log K values were further computed by different computational techniques^{7,8} and the mean values are given in Table 1. The thermodynamic formation constants were evaluated by extrapolating the determined formation constants to zero ionic strength and are given at the bottom of Table 1.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complex formation were calculated using standard equations⁹ (Table 1).

A comparison of stepwise formation constants reveals that stability decreases with increase in ionic strength and temperature i.e., lower temperature is favourable for complex formation. The order of stability follows Al(III) > Cu(II) > Be(II). The same has also been observed by other workers²⁰ with polyhydroxy ligands.

The positive entropy change in case of Al(III) is ascribed due to extensive hydration of Al(III) ion in aqueous solution which releases large number of water molecules on complexation and it may be one of the reasons which accounts for the greater stability of Al(III)-tiron complexes to Be (II)-and Cu (II)-tiron complexes.

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